

absorption maximum and extinction coefficient are found to be substituent dependent. The values of extinction coefficient are found to change in the order *p*-methyl > *o*-methoxy > *p*-methoxy > *o*-carboxy > *m*-nitro > *p*-nitro > *o*-chloro > *p*-sulphonic acid > *p*-chloro. It is found that these values do not change in a regular order and therefore could not be correlated with Hammett's sigma values. The values of absorption maxima of 3-arylidene derivatives of 2-phenylpyrrocoline show similar type of behaviour⁶.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in an open capillary in a sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 389 spectrophotometer. UV spectra (ethanol) were taken on a Toshniwal RL 02 spectrophotometer.

1-Aza-2-phenyl-3-arylazopyrrocoline (2): 1-Aza-2-phenylpyrrocolinium bromide (1.08 g) was dissolved in water and cooled in ice bath. A mixture of concentrated HCl and aniline (1 : 1) was prepared and the resulting hydrochloride was dissolved in water. An aqueous solution of calculated amount of sodium nitrite was added to the hydrochloride solution in an ice bath. The whole mixture was then added to the solution of azopyrrocolinium bromide in an ice bath and magnetically stirred for 0.5 h. The precipitate was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol-water mixture (70%), m.p. 125° (Found: C, 75.98; H, 4.5; N, 18.52. C₁₈H₈N₄ requires C, 76.51; H, 4.69; N, 18.79%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 380 nm (ε_{max} = 0.699 × 10⁴). Other azo compounds were prepared by the same method taking different substituted anilines. The analytical data are given in Table 1.

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References

1. A. SHARMA and G. B. BEHERA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 1977.
2. M. H. PALMER, "The structure and Mechanism of Heterocyclic Compounds", Edward Arnold, London, 1967 pp. 336-337.
3. S. MC. KENZIE and D. H. REID, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 145.
4. A. SHARMA and G. B. BEHERA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, 20, 1182.
5. K. KAKAYASHI, K. TENU and M. KUNIO, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1971, 10, 2016.
6. A. SHARMA and G. B. BEHERA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1976, 14, 551.

Studies on Antitubercular Agents. Preparation of 1-(4-Methoxybenzoyl)-2-benzalhydrazine and 2-Aryl-3-(4-methoxybenzamido)-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone

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SEVERAL methods for the synthesis of 4-thiazolidinones have been reported¹⁻⁴. The hydrazones of aromatic or heterocyclic aldehyde/ketone react with α-mercapto acids in benzene to give a variety of substituted-4-thiazolidinone. The present communication is intended to report the reaction of thiomalic acid with hydrazones (1) of 4-methoxybenzhydrazide, and *in vitro* tuberculostatic activity of the resulting 5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones (2). The structure of the title compounds (1 and 2) were confirmed by elemental analysis and IR spectra.

Experimental

1-(4-Methoxybenzoyl)-2-benzal hydrazine (1): The solution of 4-methoxybenzhydrazide⁵ (0.01 mol) in ethanol (95%, 25 ml) was added to benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in ethanol (95%, 15 ml). Contents were refluxed for 3 h, cooled, filtered, dried and crystallised from 95% ethanol (84%), m.p. 210° (Found: N, 10.90. C₁₅H₁₄N₂O₂ requires N, 11.02%).

2-Phenyl-3-(4-methoxybenzamido)-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone (2): 1-(4-Methoxybenzoyl)-2-benzalhydrazine (0.01 mol) and thiomalic acid (0.01 mol) were reacted in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride (0.5 g) at 160° for 2 h, then the temperature was further raised to 180° for 30 min. The product was treated with ether and water to remove unreacted hydrazone and thiomalic acid. It was dissolved in sodium hydroxide (10%) and reprecipitated with hydrochloric acid and crystallised from 95% ethanol (70%), m.p. 107° (Found: N, 7.12; S, 8.15. C₁₉H₁₈N₂O₅S requires N, 7.25; S, 8.29%).

Antimycobacterial activity: The antimycobacterial activity of compounds 1 and 2 was studied against H₃₇R_v strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in Lowenstein-Jensen's egg medium (5 ml). The retardation of the growth rate was studied upto 6 weeks at 37°. The procedure was duplicated with solvent (DMF) for control purposes. It has been concluded that all compounds (1 and 2) possess significant tuberculostatic activity at 30 µg ml⁻¹ concentration. The physical and biological data are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1*

Sl no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Antitubercular activity**		
				µg ml ⁻¹		
				0	5	30
1.	C ₆ H ₅	210	84	+	+	-
2.	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	152	88	+	+	-
3.	4-OH.C ₆ H ₄	122	86	+	+	-
4.	OH=CH.C ₆ H ₅	205	70	+	+	-
5.	4-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	180	81	+	+	-
6.	2-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	222	71	+	+	-
7.	3-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	162	68	+	+	-
8.	3-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	185	72	+	+	-
9.	4-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	235	79	+	+	-
10.	3,4-OH ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	254	74	+	+	-
11.	3-OCH ₃ .4-OH.C ₆ H ₃	179	82	+	+	-
12.	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	175	67	+	+	-
13.	3,5-Br ₂ .2-OH.C ₆ H ₃	237	85	+	+	-

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, N, S analyses.

** + = No inhibition, - = active.

TABLE 2—DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2*

Sl no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Antitubercular activity**		
				µg ml ⁻¹		
				0	5	30
1.	C ₆ H ₅	107	70	+	+	-
2.	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	130	74	+	+	-
3.	4-OH.C ₆ H ₄	128	76	+	+	-
4.	OH=CH.C ₆ H ₅	175	55	+	+	-
5.	4-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	135	64	+	+	-
6.	2-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	154	66	+	+	-
7.	3-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	115	65	+	+	-
8.	3-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	166	62	+	+	-
9.	4-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	142	61	+	+	-
10.	3,4-OH ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	113	69	+	+	-
11.	3-OCH ₃ .4-OH.C ₆ H ₃	130	72	+	+	-
12.	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	110	68	+	+	-
13.	3,5-Br ₂ .2-OH.C ₆ H ₃	158	74	+	+	-

* and ** Explanations as in Table 1.

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References

1. F. C. BROWN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1961, **61**, 463.
2. K. A. ZOLOTOROVA, I. P. MASLOVA, N. A. GLAZU NOVA, E. F. BURMISTROV and L. A. PUGACHEVA, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1966 **65** 18767.
3. G. DANILA, *Rev. Chem. (Bucharest)*, 1978, **29**, 820, 1152 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1979, **90**, 72086, 152037).
4. S. P. SINGH, S. S. PARMAR, K. RAMAN and V. I. STENBERG, *Chem. Rev.*, 1981, **81**, 176.
5. M. OLJEASN, *J. Pharm and Pharmacol.*, 1954, **6**, 127.

Studies on Isoniazide Derivatives. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-Aryl-3-(pyridylcarbonyl)-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones

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ISONIAZIDE possess tuberculostatic activity¹. 4-Thiazolidinones are also associated with various kinds of biological activities like hypnotic², anaesthetic³, antifungal⁴ etc. With a view to get more active drug, we have prepared 4-thiazolidinones of type 1 by the condensation of 4-substituted benzalisoniazides with thiomalic acid. 4-Substituted benzalisoniazides were obtained by condensing isoniazide with different aromatic aldehydes. The constitution was supported by ir spectra⁵⁻⁸. The products were screened for antimicrobial activity.

1

Ir spectra: The ir spectra of 4-thiazolidinones of type 1 were taken on KBr pellets and characterised; 1655 (C=O), 1580 (NCO) and 1600 nm (NH).

Experimental

4-Benzal isoniazide: Benzaldehyde (0.1 mol) was added to the solution of isoniazide (0.1 mol) in

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